

**SPRING WATER No. 26 AND SPRING WATER No. 27 IN
GALLAOROL DISTRICT, UZBEKISTAN**

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Gallaorol district in Jizzakh region, which is part of the mountainous region of Jizzakh region, is famous for its many springs. The results of chemical laboratory analysis of the samples taken from these springs are described in the study. Physical and chemical indicators of water (Spring water No. 26 and Spring water No. 27) are in accordance with state standards for water quality.

The springs in the Gallaorol region were named with numbers (Spring No. 26, Spring No. 27). Water samples from spring waters were placed in 1.5 liter polyethylene bottles, and their chemical analyzes was determined by a chemical analytical laboratory method.

Spring No.26, Spring No. 27 in Gallaorol district of Jizzakh region was studied. The results of the chemical analysis of the samples taken from these spring water are analyzed. The pH indicator of Spring No. 26 is 7. 6, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 1.4 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 412. 8 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be 1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 56.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 17. 0 mg/dm³, Fe - <0. 05, and meets state standards (0.3). CO₃²⁻ - < 5. 0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 215.6, SO₄²⁻ - 91.1 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl⁻ - 25.3 (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂⁻ - 0.01, NO₃⁻ - 43.2 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 4.2 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

The pH indicator of Spring No. 27 is 7. 5, which corresponds to the state standards of Uzbekistan (requirements for the quality of domestic and drinking water - 6.00-9.00), and it is weak alkaline. The SiO₂ indicator of spring water is 2.0 mg/dm³, and the indicator is suitable in the state standards. The dry residue of spring water is 436.5 mg/dm³, and the state standards state that it should be

1000.0-1500.00 mg/dm³, which means that it also meets the requirements for this indicator. The amount of Ca²⁺ from cations is 64.1 mg/dm³, the amount of Mg²⁺ is 15.8 mg/dm³, Fe - < 0.05 mg/dm³, and meets state standards (0.3). CO₃²⁻ - < 5.0 mg/dm³, HCO₃⁻ - 271.7, SO₄²⁻ - 98.7 (400.00-500.00 by standard), Cl⁻ - 19.2, (250.00-350.00 by standard), NO₂⁻ - 0.01, NO₃⁻ - 32.9 mg/dm³ conforms to state standards (45.00). The total hardness of spring water is 4.5 mg-equiv/dm³, which suitable the standard requirements (7.00-10.00).

A comparison of the results of chemical analysis of these two springs can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1.

Chemical analyze results of Spring No. 26 and Spring No. 27 (mg/dm³)

Spring name	pH	SiO ₂ mg/dm ³	Dry residue mg/dm ³	Ca ⁺ mg/dm ³	Mg ⁺ mg/dm ³	Fe mg/dm ³	CO ₃ ²⁻ mg/dm ³	HCO ₃ ⁻ mg/dm ³
Spring No. 26	7.6	1.4	412.8	56.1	17.0	< 0.05	<5.0	215.6
Spring No. 27	7.5	2.0	436.5	64.1	15.8	< 0.05	<5.0	271.7
Standard (UzDSt 951:2011)	6.00-9.00	---	1000.00-1500.00	---	---	0.3	---	---
Standard (UzDSt 0950:2011)	6.00-9.00	---	1000.00-1500.00	---	---	0.3	---	---

Spring name	SO ₄ ²⁻ mg/dm ³	Cl ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₂ ⁻ mg/dm ³	NO ₃ ⁻ mg/dm ³	Total hardness mg-equiv/dm ³
Spring No. 26	91.1	25.3	0.01	43.2	4.2
Spring No. 27	98.7	19.2	0.01	32.9	4.5
Standard (UzDSt 951:2011)	400.00-500.00	250.00-350.00	---	45.00	7.00-10.00
Standard (UzDSt 0950:2011)	400.00-500.00	250.00-350.00	---	45.00	7.00-10.00

The amount of K, Na, Mn, Pb, Cu, Cr, Zn, Ni, Co, As, CNS, Al was determined in the water of Spring No. 26 and Spring No. 27 (Table 2).

Table 2.

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 26 and Spring No. 27 (mg/dm³)

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 26

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	14.9	7	Zn	0.03
2	Na	36.8	8	Ni	0.06
3	Mn	0.01	9	Co	0.29
4	Pb	<0.02	10	As	0.07
5	Cu	0.02	11	CNS	9.7
6	Cr	0.02	12	Al	<10.0

Chemical analysis results of Spring No. 27

No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³	No.	Chemical element	mg/dm ³
1	K	13.8	7	Zn	0.01
2	Na	35.7	8	Ni	0.09
3	Mn	<0.05	9	Co	0.34
4	Pb	<0.02	10	As	0.06
5	Cu	0.01	11	CNS	9.7
6	Cr	0.04	12	Al	<10.0

Chemical analysis results (Table 1 and Table 2) Hygienic requirements and quality control for the supply of domestic drinking water to the state standards of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 951:2011) fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan, as well as drinking Hygienic requirements and quality control for drinking water fully comply with the requirements of the State Standard of Uzbekistan (UzDSt 0950:2011).

References:

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